

Hemin-collodion Membrane Electrode for Measurement of Anion Activity in Electrolytic Solutions at Different pH. Part I. Chloride-ion Activities

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A thin and uniform film of hemin (hematin hydrochloride), formed by dispersing it in a dilute solution of inert collodion (binder), could be used as a membrane electrode for determination of activity of Cl^- ions in HCl, KCl, NaCl, NH_4Cl , and LiCl in concentration range of 0.0015 to 0.050M with molarity ratio of 2 and at pH 1.3 to 3.0 in case of HCl and 4.0 to 7.4 in case of salts to which acetate or phosphate buffers are added.

Hemin, prepared from hemoglobin by treatment with HCl or a mixture of acetone and HCl at pH 2.4 to 3.6 by the method suggested by Lewis¹, has formula $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4\text{FeCl}$, when crystallised from pyridine or quinoline according to Kuester². It contains 3 active H atoms, 2 belonging to -COOH groups and the 3rd, associated with an N, according to Kuhn and Furter³; this third H belongs to one HCl, bound heteropolarly according to Lindenfeld⁴ who observed that AgNO_3 yielded AgCl with hemin and concluded hemin to be the salt of the base hematin, i.e., it is hematin hydrochloride, which is insoluble in water. Lindenfeld could replace Cl^- ion of hemin with Br^- , I^- or other acid radicals and the law of mass action was followed in this exchange. So hemin could be classified amongst anion exchangers. Again, this substance contains two -COOH groups, the H of which is replaceable by other cations at pH higher than 7, since it is soluble in alkalis.

Thin and uniform films of natural and synthetic cation and anion exchangers, capable of swelling and ionisation in presence of aqueous solutions of electrolytes, were used as membrane electrodes for determination of cation and anion activities, respectively, from the measurement of membrane potentials by Sollner and Gregor⁵, Marshall⁶, Sollner⁷, Mukherjee and Marshall⁸, Basu⁹, and many others. It has been experimentally established by them that at certain ratios of a_1/a_2 , depending on the porosity of the membrane, at certain range of concentrations of the electrolytic solutions, depending on the amount of electric charge on the membrane, and at certain value of the electric charge on the membrane due to its ionisation, the transport number of oppositely charged ion inside the membrane

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5. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 409.
6. *Ibid.*, 1939, 43, 1155; 1944, 48, 67.
7. *Ibid.*, 1945, 49, 47, 171, 265; 1946, 50, 470; 1947, 51, 299.
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becomes unity and that of the other, zero, and that the Nernst equation for the concentration potential

$$E = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_2}{a_1}$$

holds good. The general equation, suggested by Henderson, is

$$E = (2t_{\pm} - 1) \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_2}{a_1}$$

where t_+ and t_- are the transport numbers of cation and anion, respectively, inside the membrane. In the case of anion exchanger, t_- is to be considered and t_+ in the case of cation exchanger.

The object of the present work is to ascertain if hemin, containing exchangeable Cl^- ions as well as two exchangeable H^+ ions of two $-\text{COOH}$ groups per molecule, could be used for preparing a membrane electrode with +ve electric charge for the measurement of anion activity of an aqueous solution of an electrolyte and whether pH value of the solution has any influence on the membrane potential, as observed by Jacobson¹⁰ in the case of a polyampholite.

EXPERIMENTAL

As the film of hemin, obtained by melting it, was found to be brittle, the use of collodion as a binder was resorted to. The weighed quantity of finely powdered hemin (B.D.H.) was dispersed in a dilute solution of known concentration of inert collodion in a mixture of ethanol-ether (1:3) in a glass petri dish with flat surface. The mixture was constantly stirred with a glass rod till it was sufficiently viscous and then it was allowed to evaporate to dryness at the room temperature undisturbed and covered with a filter paper. The dried film, 0.12 mm thick, was cut into small circular pieces, about 1 sq. cm. each, and one of them fitted between two rubber washers to the end of a glass tube, on which a waxed metal cap could be screwed up. The tube was filled with CO_2 -free distilled water and held in the same, contained in a small pyrex glass beaker, fitted in a thermoflask containing water at 25°. The film was thus soaked in water for about 24 hours; after removing water and rinsing, it was filled with 0.1N-KCl, dipped in the same solution in the beaker, and left for about 72 hours for conditioning the membrane. After introducing small saturated calomel electrodes inside and outside the membrane in 0.01N-KCl or 0.1N-KCl and adjusting the liquid inside and outside in the same level to prevent hydrostatic pressure on the membrane, the asymmetric membrane potential was measured by means of a slide-wire box potentiometer (Pye & Co.), reading to 0.2 mv, using ballistic mirror galvanometer as nul point instrument; it was found to be zero. The film-membrane electrodes of inert collodion, used as binder, also gave zero membrane potential when KCl solutions of different concentrations were used on the two sides, the calomel electrode dipping in dilute solution being connected to -ve terminal of the potentiometer. Thus the symmetry of the hemin distribution in the film and the non-interference of the collodion were ensured.

In the case of solutions of different concentrations of uni-univalent electrolytes, HCl , KCl , NaCl , NH_4Cl , and LiCl (Merck's C.P.), it was found experimentally that at molarity

ratio 2 and concentration within the range of 0.001 to 0.05 *M*, the Nernst equation for concentration potential held good. The equilibrium was established within 15 minutes of filling the solutions and the membrane-potential reading remained constant for more than half an hour. The hemin-collidion membrane could be preserved in water containing a crystal of thymol.

The influence of *pH* on membrane potential in the case of KCl solutions with Cl⁻ ion activities inside/outside=0.00583/0.00296 was studied by using acetate buffers for *pH* 4.0 and 5.2 and phosphate buffers for *pH* 6.2, 7.4, and 8.0, prepared according to Conway¹². The same *pH* was maintained on both sides of the membrane by using the buffers of the same concentration, in which the required quantity of solid KCl was dissolved; the *pH* of the two solutions was confirmed by testing with a Cambridge *pH*-meter.

The experimental and theoretical values of membrane potentials are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Membrane potentials in the case of solutions of various electrolytes of diff. conc. at molarity ratio of 2 at 25°.

Cl ⁻ ion activities (inside/outside).	Observed membrane potential (mv).					Calc. value. (mv)
	HCl.	KCl.	NaCl.	NH ₄ Cl.	LiCl.	
0.00296/0.00146	17.8	17.5	17.6	17.4	17.4	18.1
0.00583/0.00297	17.2	17.0	17.2	17.6	17.2	17.3
0.01143/0.00583	17.6	17.6	16.9	16.8	17.0	17.2
0.02220/0.01143	16.7	16.5	16.5	17.0	17.2	17.0
0.04220/0.02220	16.5	16.2	16.6	16.1	16.4	16.6

TABLE II

Influence of pH on the membrane potential in the case of KCl solutions having Cl⁻ ion activities, inside/outside = 0.00583/0.00296, at 25°.

Buffer.	<i>pH</i> .	Membrane potential.		Transport No. of anion inside the membrane from obs. values.
		Obs.	Calc.	
Acetate	4.0	16.4 mv	17.3 mv	0.96
"	5.2	16.4	17.3	0.96
Phosphate	6.2	16.5	17.3	0.96
"	7.4	16.9	17.3	0.98
"	8.0	18.4	17.3	..

DISCUSSION

Table I records the membrane potentials in the case of aqueous solutions of HCl, KCl, NaCl, NH₄Cl, and LiCl of the normalities (1) 0.0030/0.0015, (2) 0.0062/0.003, (3) 0.0125/0.00625, (4) 0.025/0.0125, and (5) 0.050/0.025. The individual activity coefficients of Cl⁻ ion at

various concentrations at 25° were obtained from the graph, plotted with the values recorded by Conway¹², and the Cl⁻ ion activities calculated therefrom. It is observed that the membrane potentials in case of solutions of HCl at pH 1.3 to 3.0 and of various uni-univalent salts at pH 6.7 are nearly the same at different concentrations and at the molarity ratio 2; this shows that only Cl⁻ ions are playing the part and the membrane is maintaining the same amount of +ve charge at pH 1.3 to 6.7. It is concluded that hemin is not behaving as a polyampholyte and so it has no zwitter ions. According to Jacobson¹⁰, the membrane potential of a polyampholyte (formed from monomers, methacrylic acid and *N*-diethyl-amino-2-ethyl methacrylate) film membrane is —ve at lower pH 3.0 to 4.0 and decreases continuously with pH; it is zero at isoelectric point, pH 6.1, and becomes +ve at higher pH, 6.2 to 7.5. The observed membrane potentials vary from the calculated ones slightly within the experimental error of ±3% within the range of concentration of 0.0015 to 0.05 M at molarity ratio 2; at higher concentrations and higher ratios, the Nernst equation did not hold good, the observed membrane potential being lower than the calculated values, perhaps due to less ionisation of hemin on account of the tendency of Cl⁻ ion to combine coordinately with Fe, as suggested by Machly and Akoson¹¹, and high porosity of hemin-collodion film respectively.

Table II records the values of membrane potentials of KCl solutions, the pH of which was adjusted by acetate buffer for values 4.0 and 5.2 and by phosphate buffer for values 6.2, 7.4, and 8.0. The observed membrane potential was constant at pH 4.0 to 6.2; there was a slight increase at 7.4 and at 8.0 there was a sharp fall from 16.9 to 13.4 mv. This shows that at pH 8, the alkali reacts with -COOH groups of hemin and consequently the electric charge on the membrane changes from +ve to —ve; at pH higher than 8.0, hemin dissolves. The calculated membrane potential is higher by 0.8-0.9 mv than the observed values 16.4-16.5 at pH 4.0 to 6.2, which cannot be attributed to the presence of buffers since according to Jacobson¹⁰, the concentration of the buffers, and hence the activities of the acetate or phosphate ions on both sides, being the same, the bi-ionic potential is minimised, and Cl⁻ becomes the chief potential-determining ion on the two sides of the membrane.

The membrane-potential work with other halides and other salts of hematin is in progress. The author is thankful to Prof. C. S. Narwani for suggesting and guiding this problem.

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